

Metabarcoding reveals the effect of land cover and temporal variations on the diet of Brown long-eared and Soprano pipistrelle bats within a unique European habitat, the pasture dominated landscapes of Ireland.

Hurpy^{1.}, G., Aughney^{2.} T., Skujina^{1,3.} I., Roche^{4.} N. and Teeling^{1.} E. C*.

¹ School of Biology and Environmental Science, University College Dublin, Belfield, Dublin 4, Ireland.

² Bat Eco Services Limited, Virginia, Co. Cavan, Ireland.

³ Genome Stability Laboratory, School of Biological and Chemical Sciences, University of Galway, University Road, Galway, Ireland.

⁴ Bat Conservation Ireland Carmichael House 4-7, North Brunswick Street, Dublin 7, Ireland .

*Corresponding author: emma.teeling@ucd.ie

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Supporting Table S1: Number of faecal samples collected at each bat maternity roost over the three years of sampling (2021-2023). 1st sampling period : Gestation ; 2nd sampling period : Lactation ; 3rd sampling period : Post-lactation. Numbers of faecal samples included in the analyses, after that bat species was confirmed, are indicated between parentheses. The sub-total lines show the total of number of faecal samples collected per bat species. The total line presents the combined total for the two bat species. The numbers indicated in the “roost column” correspond to the numbers assigned to each roost in Fig. 1.

Bat species	Roost	2021 sampling collections			2022 sampling collections			2023 sampling collections			TOTAL
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	
Soprano pipistrelle <i>Pipistrellus pygmaeus</i>	Glendalough (1)	16(16)	135(20)	77(20)	25(20)	42(20)	91(20)	23(20)	45(20)	36(20)	490(176)
	Kilafin (2)	/	/	/	7(7)	13(13)	11(10)	5(1)	20(19)	23(20)	79(70)
	Birr (3)	30(0)	41(12)	36(15)	11(7)	26(13)	15(10)	45(20)	23(20)	12(12)	239(109)
	Dromore wood (4)	/	/	/	54(20)	72(20)	29(20)	30(20)	40(20)	28(20)	253(120)
	Sub-total	46(16)	176(32)	113(35)	97(54)	153(66)	146(61)	103(61)	128(79)	99(72)	1061(475)
Brown long-eared bat <i>Plecotus auritus</i>	Ennisnag (5)	31(17)	10(2)	6(5)	43(16)	36(20)	20(6)	17(14)	33(12)	27(15)	223(107)
	Glengarriff (6)	39(18)	47(16)	52(12)	19(18)	11(11)	22(20)	50(20)	38(20)	63(18)	341(153)
	Inagh (7)	197 (20)	103(20)	97(20)	11(11)	119(20)	55(20)	56(20)	46(20)	48(20)	732(171)
	Kinvarra (8)	78(20)	108(20)	168(20)	68(20)	171(20)	76(20)	79(20)	33(20)	71(20)	852(180)
	Letterfrack (9)	11(10)	19(18)	182(19)	20(20)	52(20)	64(20)	54(20)	97(20)	45(20)	544(167)
	Carra James (10)	43(20)	46(20)	30(20)	26(20)	30(20)	30(20)	33(20)	27(20)	23(20)	288(180)
	Milltown (11)	35(19)	26(0)	48(17)	26(20)	30(20)	30(20)	30(20)	34(20)	38(20)	297(156)
	Killmore (12)	11(11)	96(16)	17(17)	21(17)	54(20)	22(14)	12(12)	24(16)	32(20)	289(143)
	Sub-total	445 (135)	455 (112)	600 (130)	234 (142)	503 (151)	319 (140)	331 (146)	332 (148)	347 (153)	3566 (1257)
TOTAL	491 (151)	631 (145)	713 (165)	331 (196)	656 (217)	465 (201)	434 (207)	460 (228)	446 (225)	4627 (1732)	

Supporting Table S2: NucleoSpin Plant kit extraction protocol (adapted from Zarzoso-Lacoste et al., 2018).

NucleoSpin Plant kit extraction protocol (adapted from Zarzoso-Lacoste et al., 2018)
1. Sample preparation
Add carefully 0.01 gr of pooled faeces into 2mL tube
2. Cell lysing Buffer PL2 and PL3
Add 400 µL Buffer PL2 and 10 µL RNase to each tube strips containing faeces sample and close using new cap strips. Mix by vigorous shaking for 15–30 s. Spin for 30 s at 11 000 rpm to collect any sample from the Cap Strips.
Incubate samples at 60°C overnight, on dry bath.
Carefully add 100 µL Buffer PL3 to each sample and close the tubes, mix thoroughly, and incubate for 15 min on ice to precipitate sodium dodecyl sulfate completely.
3. Filtrate lysate
Place NucleoSpin filter (violet ring) into new collection tube 2mL
Load all lysate and centrifuge for 2min at 11 000 g.
Collect filtered lysate into a new 1.5 Eppendorf tube and discard filter
4. Adjust DNA binding condition
Predispose 450 µL Buffer PC in 1.5mL Eppendorf
Add 400 µL clear lysate and mix thoroughly by pipetting five times
5. Bind DNA
Label green column and place it on new column
Transfer 700 µL of lysate to column and centrifuge for 2 min at 14 000 rpm and discard flow through
6. Wash and dry silica membrane
Add 400 µL PW1 Buffer and centrifuge for 1 min at 14 000 rpm
Add 700 µL PW2 Buffer and centrifuge for 1 min at 14 000 rpm
Add 700 µL PW2 Buffer and centrifuge for 1 min at 14 000 rpm
Centrifuge at 14 000 rpm for 10 min
7. Elute DNA
Place column in labelled 1.5 Eppendorf
Dispose PE Buffer 75 µL into column (pre-heated at 70°C) and incubate at 70°C for 2 min
Centrifuge 2 min at 14 000 rpm
Dispose PE Buffer 75 µL into column (pre-heated at 70°C) and incubate at 70°C for 2 min
Centrifuge 2 min at 14 000 rpm
Dispose in - 20°C freezer of use for PCR immediately

Supporting Figure S1. Sample completeness curves for each maternity roost by year and for each sampling period. Curves were created with *iNEXT* and *ggiNEXT* packages, with $q = 0$. Rarefaction curve (solid line) represents the expected sample completeness as the sample size increases. Extrapolation curve (dashed line) predicts the potential sample completeness beyond the observed sample size. A - H : Brown long-eared bat roosts; I - L : Soprano pipistrelle roosts..

B

Carra James – Brown long-eared bat

2021

2022

2023

c

Ennismag – Brown long-eared bat

2021

2022

2023

D

Glengarriff – Brown long-eared bat

2021

2022

2023

m

Inagh – Brown long-eared bat

2021

2022

2023

F

Killmore – Brown long-eared bat

G

Milltown – Brown long-eared bat

2021

2022

2023

H

Letterfrack – Brown long-eared bat

2021

2022

2023

I
Dromore wood – Soprano pipistrelle

J
Kilafin – Soprano pipistrelle

K

Glendalough – Soprano pipistrelle

2021

2022

2023

L

Birr – Soprano pipistrelle

Supporting Figure S2

Mean richness of main arthropod orders (*Lepidoptera* and *Diptera*) in the diet of Brown long-eared bat (A) and Soprano pipistrelle (B) across all sampling periods. Horizontal lines at each point represent standard deviation values

Supplementary Figure S3

Web plots showing interactions between the Brown long-eared bat (S.3A) and Soprano Pipistrelle (S.3B) and prey of Lepidoptera (a) and Diptera (b) families across maternity roosts. Percentages show the percentage of each order in diets. The web plot was created using the 'bipartiteD3' function from the bipartiteD3 package.

a Brown long-eared bat

b Brown long-eared bat

Supplementary Figure S.3A

Supplementary Figure S.3B

Supporting Table S3: Details of outliers discarded for the nMDS analysis.

SampleID	Bat species	Roost	Year	Sampling period	nMDS1	nMDS2
D1586_21	Soprano pipistrelle	Glendalough	2023	Gestation	-2879.1	1153.415
D1631_23	Brown long-eared bat	Killmore	2023	Post-lactation	-10.7066	-1.50344
D3_2	Brown long-eared bat	Killmore	2021	Gestation	-2.88731	-2.34257
D1426_13	Brown long-eared bat	Killmore	2022	Post-lactation	-0.34752	-1.21338
D1426_12	Brown long-eared bat	Killmore	2022	Post-lactation	-0.31472	-1.21219
D1118_14	Brown long-eared bat	Glengarriff	2022	Gestation	-0.28079	-1.22061
D1155_5	Soprano pipistrelle	Kilafin	2022	Lactation	-0.02778	-1.21098
D589_14	Brown long-eared bat	Killmore	2021	Post-lactation	-0.27187	-1.2112
D589_16	Brown long-eared bat	Killmore	2021	Post-lactation	-0.26608	-1.2135
D589_6	Brown long-eared bat	Killmore	2021	Post-lactation	-0.26603	-1.2135
D51_31	Brown long-eared bat	Miltown	2021	Gestation	-0.26425	-0.21315
D779_14	Brown long-eared bat	Letterfrack	2021	Post-lactation	3350.001	991.1094
D1625_19	Brown long-eared bat	Letterfrack	2023	Post-lactation	-0.02771	-1.5773

Supporting Information Figure S4

Non-metric multidimensional scaling plot showing the dissimilarity in diet composition across bat species (Top) and Brown long-eared with all samples included (Bottom).

